

Synthesis of some *N*-substituted-1,4-benzothiazinones

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Reaction of 2-aminobenzethiol with oxalyl chloride in presence of triethylamine in benzene gives 1,4-benzothiazine-2,3-dione (1) which when *N*-alkylated with chloroacetone forms *N*-(2'-propanonyl)-1,4-benzothiazine-2,3-dione (2). Base catalysed intramolecular cyclisation of 2 yields tricyclic compound 3. Further reaction of 2 with substituted arylhydrazides forms the corresponding hydrazones (4a-l). The reaction of 4 with mercaptoacetic acid in DMF in presence of ZnCl₂ gives the corresponding substituted 4-thiazolidinones (5a-f).

The benzothiazines containing four-membered azetidinone and five-membered thiazolidinone rings at 4-position show better antibacterial and antifungal activity¹. 1,4-Benzothiazines resemble structurally to phenothiazines which possess a wide spectrum of biological activities and its several derivatives are in clinical use¹⁻³. One of the structural specificities considered responsible to impart activities is a fold along nitrogen and sulfur axis in phenothiazines which is also present in 1,4-benzothiazines and therefore, they are anticipated to possess biological activities similar to phenothiazines. It has been reported that the molecules having 1,4-benzothiazine moiety have been reported to possess Aldose Reductase inhibition, Ca²⁺ antagonism, immunomodulating properties, antagonism of α₂-adrenoreceptors and anti-inflammatory activity³. Hence, the synthesis of some new *N*¹-substituted-1,4-benzothiazinone derivatives is reported.

Results and Discussion

Benzothiazine-2,3-dione (1) is *N*-alkylated by reacting with chloroacetone to form 2. The disappearance of signal due to CONH proton and appearance of two signals at δ 2.1 and 4.15 due to COCH₃ and N-CH₂ proton, respectively, confirmed the formation of 2. Compound 2 when cyclised in presence of sodium methoxide formed tricyclic compound 3, the formation of which was confirmed by the disappearance of signal at δ 2.15 due to COCH₃. Further, the nucleophilic condensation of 2 with a variety of substituted hydrazides gave the hydrazones (4a-l). The appearance of NH of CONH protons at δ 10.53 and their corresponding IR spectra indicated the formation of hydrazones. Cyclocondensation of mercaptoacetic acid with the hydrazone 4 gave the desired heterocycle *N*-substituted alkythiazolidinones (5). The appearance of an additional

signal due to S-CH₂ at δ 3.58 and shifting of signal due to CH₃ at δ 1.5 confirmed their formation.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Bruker Ac 300F spectrometer (300 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compounds was

checked by TLC using silica gel G.

1,4-Benzothiazine-2,3-dione (1) : To a solution of 2-aminothiophenol (0.016 mol) in benzene (15 ml), triethylamine (0.0003 mol) and oxalyl chloride (0.016 mol) were added in small portions with stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h on an oil-bath. The solid obtained was dissolved in 5% ethanolic NaOH (20 ml) by heating on a water-bath for 20 min. The neutralization of the resultant mixture with dil. HCl gave a solid which was crystallised from 50% ethanol, (95%), m.p. 260°; ν_{\max} 3220–3140 (NH), 1680 (C=O), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 6.35–7.1 (4H, m, ArH), 10.45 (1H, s, CONH exchangeable with D_2O).

N-(2'-Propanonyl)-1,4-benzothiazine-2,3-dione (2) : A mixture of **1** (0.05 mol), chloroacetone (0.13 mol) and K_2CO_3 (2 g) was refluxed on an oil-bath for 30 h, then cooled, filtered and the filtrate concentrated to get a solid which was crystallised from 50% ethanol, (40%), m.p. 125°; ν_{\max} 1730–1715 (C=O), 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.15 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.0 (2H, s, N- CH_2), 7.2–8.25 (4H, m, ArH).

1,2-Dihydro-2,4-dioxo-4H-pyrrolo[2,1-c]-1,4-benzothiazine (3) : A mixture of **2** (0.005 mol) and sodium methoxide (0.005 mol) in methanol (5 ml) was refluxed on an oil-bath for ~4 h. The separated solid was washed with methanol (2 ml) and crystallised from DMF, (15%), m.p. >300°; ν_{\max} 3500 (enolic OH), 1670 (C=O), 1640 cm^{-1} (conjugated C=O); δ 3.8 (2H, s, N- CH_2), 6.7–8.25 (5H, m, ArH and CH).

4-(N-2'-Arylhydrazidopropanyl)-1,4-benzothiazine-2,3-dione (4a-I) : To a mixture of **2** (0.25 mmol) and 2-methylphenoxyacetic acid hydrazide (0.25 mmol), two drops of acetic acid were added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and the separated solid crystallized from DMF to get **4a** (48%), m.p. 215°; ν_{\max} 3310 (NH), 1700–1690 (C=O), 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 1.92 (3H, s, =C- CH_3), 2.25 (3H, s, Ar CH_3), 3.35 (2H, s, N- CH_2), 4.27 (2H, s, OCH_2), 6.5–7.25 (4H, m, ArH), 7.72 (2H, d, ArH), 8.65 (2H, d, ArH), 10.53 (1H, s, CONH). Compounds **4b-I** (yields 37–53%) were prepared using the same procedure : **4b**, m.p.

270°; **c**, 218°; ν_{\max} 3300 (NH), 1700 (C=O), 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N); **d**, 195°; **e**, 215°; ν_{\max} 3300–3200 (NH), 1700 (C=O), 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N); **f**, 221°; ν_{\max} 3300–3210 (NH), 1700 (C=O), 1640 (C=O), 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N); **g**, 198°; **h**, 225°; **i**, 228°; **j**, 160°; **k**, 243°; ν_{\max} 3300 (NH), 1705 (cyclic C=O), 1660 (six-membered cyclic C=O), 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N); **l**, 222°.

N-(3-Acylamino-2-methyl-4-oxothiazolidin-2-yl)methyl-1,4-benzothiazine-2,3-dione (5a-f) : To a mixture of **4b** (0.0005 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.001 mol) in DMF (5 ml), a pinch of anhydrous zinc chloride was added and the reaction mixture heated on a steam-bath for 6 h. The separated solid (**5a**) was then crystallised from DMF, (35%), m.p. >300°; ν_{\max} 3500 (enolic OH), 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 1.5 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.6 (2H, s, S- CH_2), 3.8 (2H, s, N- CH_2), 4.55 (2H, s, OCH_2), 6.6–7.25 (8H, m, ArH), 10.5 (1H, s, CONH). Compounds **5b-f** (yields 37–41%) were prepared using the same procedure. M.ps. of all compounds, >300°.

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